
ANALYTICAL PROCEDURES USED IN EQUITY AUDITS

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Abstract: The article deals with topical issues of analytical procedures application in audit. In particular, it considers the features of analytical procedures application at the stages of audit in an economic entity, actions performed by the auditor, the order of using the results of applied analytical procedures, as well as the issues of their improvement on the basis of international auditing standards. Also in the article on the basis of practical data using analytical procedures the interrelation of equity capital with other indicators of the subject is studied and the relevant conclusions are presented.

Keywords: audit, audit stages, analytical procedures, audit planning, substantive procedures, going concern, equity capital, methods of analysis, factor analysis.

INTRODUCTION

Competition in the audit services market is increasing year by year, so the head of the audit organization is required to monitor the prices of audit services and control the costs of the audit and bring them to an acceptable level. In this case, the level of labor costs for conducting the audit is of great importance. Analytical procedures are one of the main methods for optimizing the level of labor costs and collecting audit evidence. Analytical procedures provide the auditor with the necessary amount of information at a lower cost than detailed testing.

Also, as we mentioned above, one of the main goals of the audit is to determine the continuity of business activity, reserves for effective use of financial resources, and to develop measures to improve the financial situation. And this, of course, is achieved through a deep and complex analysis of the activity of the business entity.

It should be emphasized that analytical procedures are an important and complex tool used by the auditor to obtain audit evidence. In our opinion, analytical procedures involve evaluating financial information based on the possible and expected relationships between financial and non-financial information collected by the auditor. This process may involve comparing information and using complex models based on their interrelationships. Given these circumstances, and given the limited scope of the audit, and the fact that the fee is pre-determined by the client, the auditor will try to determine the most effective procedures possible.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The use of analytical procedures in audit studies has been considered by a number of foreign and domestic scholars in their scientific works.

Analytical procedures are an assessment of financial information based on the study of objective relationships between financial and non-financial information. Analytical procedures also include the study of identified deviations and correlations that are inconsistent with other information related to the activity or that significantly differ from expected results [1].

In particular, one of our local scientists, A. Avlokulov, emphasizes that "The main goal of an audit is to form an objective audit conclusion. The formation of an audit conclusion depends on the results of a thorough examination. It is advisable to widely use analytical procedures in this process. It is precisely analytical procedures that are the most widespread and reliable method of obtaining audit evidence" [2].

I. Choriev "In increasing the quality of audit activity, reducing its labor and time capacity, the use of analytical operations is of great importance. It was concluded that by applying analytical procedures, the risk of non-detection based on the identification of "danger zones" in financial statements is minimized, the quality of audit inspection increases, and the cost capacity is reduced"[3].

According to foreign scientists, E.A. Arens and Dj.K. Lobbek, "analytical actions mean the evaluation of financial information based on the study of possible relationships between financial and non-financial information, including the comparison of financial reporting data with the expected indicators determined by the auditor" [4].

R. Hayes, R. Dassen, and others noted that "Analytical procedures involve the study of comparisons and correlations in order to substantiate the correctness of account balances and certain indicators. Such procedures help the auditor to look at the situation as a whole and to find an answer to the question of whether the financial information presented is material" [5].

From the above considerations, it is clear that there are different approaches among scholars to the application of analytical procedures in the audit process in private equity auditing. However, the application of analytical procedures at the stages of the audit has not been studied holistically, and therefore conducting research on this topic is a pressing issue today.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In accordance with the International Standard on Auditing No. 520, "Analytical Procedures," the use of analytical procedures is required in an audit. In our opinion, analytical procedures make it possible to ensure the effectiveness of the audit at a low cost. Analytical procedures are used in most cases to increase the reliability of the audit:

- to analyze objective relationships between data and form the auditor's opinion about the organization and its activities;
- to predict values that allow comparing actual indicators;
- to study detected deviations and relationships that are inconsistent with other information relevant to the audit or that differ significantly from expected results.

Analytical procedures are inherently part of audit procedures and can be used at all stages of an audit. It is worth emphasizing that we believe that the use of analytical procedures is appropriate when the organization's internal control system is effective and information obtained from external sources is reliable.

The purpose of applying analytical procedures is to obtain relevant and reliable audit evidence and to draw an overall conclusion about the extent to which the financial statements correspond to the auditor's perceptions of the entity.

Analytical procedures used in the audit should be economically justified, that is, the effectiveness of its application should be higher than the costs. Analytical procedures are used at all stages of the audit.

- Therefore, the auditor can use analytical procedures at the stages of the audit, depending on the purpose set for him. In our opinion, the main purpose of using analytical procedures at the planning stage, which is the initial stage of the audit, is to:

- understand the business processes of the business entity;
- assess changes in financial reporting indicators during the reporting period. If the audit is not being conducted for the first time, the current year's accounting and reporting data are compared with the audited information of the previous year;
- determine the level of risks that may arise in the financial statements for the department to be audited;
- reduce the scope of application of detailed testing procedures. If unusual deviations are not observed when applying analytical procedures at the planning stage, material misstatements in the financial statements are considered insignificant. In this case, it is possible to reduce the detailed testing procedures used to study account balances and turnover for the department being audited;
- determining the criteria for assessing the level of importance;
- risk assessment and planning the size of the expected inspection package;
- drawing up a program of actions based on the essence.

In our opinion, at this stage, the auditor should determine the minimum and maximum limits of unusual deviations based on regulatory documents, internal procedures, materiality, or professional judgment. This situation helps the auditor decide whether or not to perform additional testing. Therefore, if the identified unusual deviations have a significant impact on the financial statements and related information, the auditor should request explanations and documentation from the accounting department. If the auditor decides that the explanations for the identified deviations are insufficient, the auditor should classify the financial statements as misstated and perform additional testing. The actions that the auditor performs at this stage are presented in Figure 1.

The final stage of the audit is the assessment of the financial condition and going concern of the entity, as well as the significance of any identified deviations, using analytical procedures. From this we can conclude that the purpose of the audit is not only to express an opinion on the reliability of the financial statements and related information, but also to assess the going concern status of the entity, that is, its ability to continue its activities in the foreseeable future. This is because financial statements are prepared on the basis of this assumption, going concern. International Accounting Standard No. 1, "Presentation of Financial Statements," requires the management of the entity to assess the entity's ability to continue as a going concern. The auditor's task is to obtain sufficient appropriate audit evidence about the appropriateness of the entity's management's use of the going concern basis of accounting in preparing the financial statements and to consider whether there is a material uncertainty about the entity's ability to continue as a going concern.

Figure 1. The auditor's actions in the application of analytical procedures¹.

¹ Made by author

CONCLUSION.

1. Analytical actions in the audit serve to increase the work efficiency of auditors and ensure the quality of work. Auditors independently determine the actions used in the audit process based on their professional judgment. In this case, the main focus is on the actions used to enable gathering of sufficient and reliable evidence on the subject of the audit. In short, there is a direct relationship between the type of analytical procedure chosen and the accuracy it can provide. In general, the more accurate the analytical procedures used, the higher the reliability of the information obtained by these procedures.

2. Analytical procedures play an important role in a risk-based audit approach. Analytical procedures, properly designed and performed, allow the auditor to achieve audit objectives more effectively by reducing or replacing other detailed audit procedures.

3. The effectiveness of analytical procedures depends on the auditor's understanding of the entity's business environment and the use of professional judgment. Therefore, analytical procedures should be performed or reviewed by highly qualified members of the audit team.

4. Conclusions drawn from the results of analytical procedures designed and performed in an established manner allow the auditor to confirm the conclusions drawn during the audit of individual components or elements of the financial statements. This helps the auditor to draw appropriate conclusions that can be used as a basis for the audit opinion.

REFERENCES:

1. The International Standard of Audit (ISA) 520 “Analytical procedures”. www.iasplus.com
2. Avlokulov A.Z. Improving the application of analytical procedures based on international auditing standards / Economy and education / 2020 No. 6. Page 234.
3. Choriev I.Kh. Methodological aspects of using analytical procedures to detect errors in financial statements / Scientific Journal of “International Finance & Accounting” Issue 1, February 2023. ISSN: 2181-1016.
4. Arens E.A., Lobbeck Dj.K. Audit. M.: Finance and statistics, 2003. 235 p.
5. Rick Hayes, Roger Dassen, Arnold Schilder, Philip Wallage, «PRINCIPLES OF AUDITING» Second edition published by Pearson Education Limited 2005. 318-p.